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西安交通大学
XI'AN JIAOTONG UNIVERSITY

3D Printing of Continuous Sized Carbon Fiber Reinforced PA6 Composites

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Research background

- 3D printing of continuous fiber reinforced composites (CFRTP-FDM) have the advantages of simple forming process, low cost and mold-less, and capability to produce complex structure, but low mechanical properties are caused by poor interfacial performance with the use of dry fiber.

◆ Advantages

Simple process, low cost and complex structure

◆ Disadvantages

Low performance and poor interface

Experiments

- To promote the interfacial performance, a solution infiltration process is performed to pre-treat carbon fiber and obtain new sized carbon fiber (SCF), and SCF are used to print composites by our 3D printer.

Results and discussion

- Through solution infiltration process, a new thermoplastic polyamide sizing layer is coated onto the fiber surface and there are some polyamide solids between carbon fibers in some areas, indicating that pre-impregnation also achieves during the sizing treatment.

Surface chemical compositions and surface morphology of single VCF and SCF, and cross-section of SCF bundle

Results and discussion

- Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) increases from 18.04 MPa for VCF/PA6 to 25.65 MPa for SCF/PA6 by 42.2%. Fibers pull-out and layers delamination are happen in VCF/PA6, while not observed in SCF/PA6.

Results and discussion

- Tensile and flexural properties of SCF/PA6 are both dramatically improved compared with VCF/PA6.

Tensile and flexural properties of VCF/PA6 and SCF/PA6

Results and discussion

- Compared with 3D printed virgin carbon fiber (VCF) composites, the interfacial properties and mechanical performance of sized carbon fiber composites are improved dramatically.

◆ **Poor** interfacial performance of VCF/PA6

◆ **Enhanced** Interfacial performance of SCF/PA6

Conclusions

- Fiber-matrix interface in the 3D printed continuous fiber composites not only means the impregnation of melt matrix into the fiber bundle but also means the adhesion between them, and the sizing treatment process can promote both two aspects of interfacial performance to improve the mechanical properties .

Composition of fiber-matrix interface in CFRTP-FDM

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***Thank you for your
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